

Lähetäjä: info@legumehub.eu
Lähetetty: perjantai 28. tammikuuta 2022 12.51
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Aihe: Legume Hub Members' Newsletter 2
Liitteet: Legume_Hub_members_January_2022.pdf; Legume Hub - Content and members analysis.pdf; Minutes of founding meeting - European Legume Hub Association.pdf

Legume Hub Members' Newsletter 2

The Legume Hub is growing

28 January 2022

The purpose of this newsletter is to keep you informed about the development of your Legume Hub and to support interaction between members and with those who manage and administer the Hub for you.

The Legume Hub is a mutually-owned self-publishing platform for all interested in the development of legume production and use in Europe. We want to bring that ambition to life. We are now in the closing months of the Legumes Translated project and we are concentrating on setting up the best possible conditions for the continued growth of the Hub into the future. We have made a good start, but there is still a lot to do if we are to realise the potential. A detailed analysis of the contents already available on the Hub is attached. A step-by-step video for creating a pdf upload can be found [here](#).

Donal Murphy-Bokern
Chairman

Founding meeting of the European Legume Hub Association

The board of the European Legume Hub Association was elected and the statutes were approved at the founding meeting on 22 November 2021. For more information, please visit the '[About us](#)' section on the Legume Hub.

Continued growth

The Legume Hub Community (Association) currently consists of 104 members. Membership has risen steadily since the launch last July. Also, the number of contributions is rising steadily. Please see the attached documents on content and member analysis as well as the list of Legume Hub members for further details.

Our projects

All research project teams and consortia that support the development and use of legume crops in Europe are welcome to use the Hub as a platform for communication. They can use the Hub to build a suite of communications within the Hub framework. At the same time, members of all consortia can use the Hub as their personal publishing platform, including the facility to self-publish Hub articles. The Hub combines the convenience of self-publishing articles that link research and crop development practice with the quality assurance provided by peer review. Currently the Hub provides a publication platform for six projects. To find out more, please visit ['Our projects'](#) on the Legume Hub website.

More technical functionality

Since the first newsletter in August 2021, two more language modules were implemented on the Hub. Beside English and German, we now also feature Romanian and Russian.

The Legume Hub secretariat is currently working on a [blog](#) for the Hub. It will be called 'Legume [Viewpoints](#)' and give members to opportunity to express their opinion on broader topics around legumes. The Legume [Viewpoints](#) section will be available from February.

The next feature will be an image gallery, giving members the possibility to upload and hence store and share images on legumes. The image gallery will be available in spring 2022.

Funded by the
European Union

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